

FEATURES OF DAMAGE TO UPPER JAWS

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Abstract.

The article is devoted to a review of literary sources that classify Guerin's fractures. According to scientific research, the classifications developed by clinicians are mainly given. The existing medico-legal classifications do not fully illustrate the variants of injuries and expert aspects. The variety of the upper jaw injuries requires the acceptance of the unified medico-legal classification, embodying all necessary qualifying criteria.

Keywords.

Guerin's fractures, classification, criteria, medico-legal examination.

Guerin's fractures reach 3.3% of the total number of maxillo-facial area traumas (P.Z. Arzhantsev et al., 1975). Currently, maxillo-facial bone injuries make up 2.5-4.5% of all skeletal bone injuries [1, 2, 6, 9].

It has been established that the most frequent causes of maxillofacial bone injuries are: domestic (64.4-95.5%), transport (3.7-13.3%) and sports (1.6-3.3%) trauma [1, 2, 6, 11].

Classification of Guerin's fractures and their complications (A.A. Timofeeva, 1998): I. Isolated fractures of the upper jaw: 1. Fractures of the upper jaw body: unilateral (sagittal); typical (according to the classification of Le Fort, Wismund); combined; atypical. 2. Fractures of the alveolar process of maxilla: alveolar; frontal; palatine. 3. Comminuted fractures (body and processes). II. Combined fractures of the upper jaw: with craniocerebral injury, with injuries of other bones, with soft tissue injuries. III. Complications of Guerin's fractures: 1. Early complications (injury and displacement of the eyeball, vascular and nerve injuries, subcutaneous facial emphysema, meningitis, etc.). 2. Late complications (paralysis of the facial musculature, ptosis, osteomyelitis, sinusitis, facial deformity, etc.).

G.A. Pashinian et al. in their analysis of the peculiarities of the mechanism of mandibular fracture trauma (565 cases) found that the recent fractures were most

frequently caused by domestic trauma (85.7% of observations), transport (11.3%), sports (1.4%) and industrial (1.1%) trauma [3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9].

In addition to X-ray studies, modern methods of computerized diagnosis of jaw fractures are also widely used in clinical practice [3, 4, 9,10].

In current medical practice, the classification of R. Le Fort (1901), who described the different types of fractures that he identified experimentally, is used to determine the types of Guerin's fractures, taking into account modern diagnostic technologies. According to the description of R. Le Fort the fracture lines go: upper (Le Fort I) - through the nasal bones, the frontal process of the upper jaw, the fundus of the eye cavity, and then through frontozygomatic suture to the pterygoid process of the basilar bone; the middle (Le Fort II) - through the nasal bones, the frontal process of the upper jaw, the fundus of the eye cavity, zygomaticomaxillary suture, and then to the pterygoid processes; the lower (Le Fort III) - parallel to the base of the alveolar process.

Classification of Guerin's fractures according to localization (Le Fort, 1901): 1. Fractures of the alveolar process. 2. Guerin's fractures according to Le Fort I (inferior type of fracture). 3. Guerin's fractures according to Le Fort II (middle type of fractures). 4. Guerin's fractures according to Le Fort III (superior type of fractures). When hit by a hard object with a wide surface, usually an indirect fracture occurs in the weakest areas of the upper jaw outside the area of the traumatic force (e.g. in the area where the upper jaw meets the facial bones and skull base, alveolar bone detachment, etc.).

Inferior fracture type (Le Fort I). The fracture line goes horizontally over the alveolar process and the roof of the hard palate, from the base of the piriform aperture on both sides, to the back and above the floor of sinus, passing through the tubercle and the lower third of the pterygoid process of sphenoid bone. In this type of fracture, the floor of the nose and the floor of sinus breaks off and there is a horizontal fracture of the nasal septum (Fig. 1). The victim complains about pain in the upper jaw, which increases with clenching and chewing; numbness of the teeth and gingival mucosa; improper occlusion of the teeth; feeling of a debris in the pharynx; vomiting; difficulty breathing through the nose and nosebleed.

Figure 1. Guerin's fracture inferior type according to Le Fort I

The middle type of fracture (Le Fort II). In Guerin's fracture according to Le Fort II, the fracture line goes to the junction of the frontal process of the upper jaw

with the nasal part of the frontal bone and the nasal bones (nasofrontal suture), then goes down the medial orbital wall to the inferior orbital fissure. The fracture line runs down the inferior wall of the orbital cavity to the infraorbital margin, crossing it at or near the zygomaticomaxillary suture. The fracture line may go through the infraorbital foramen. Along the anterior wall of the maxillary sinus along the zygomaticomaxillary suture it passes to the back of the maxillary tuber and the pterygoid process of sphenoid bone. In a bilateral fracture, the nasal septum and the ethmoid bone can be fractured (Fig. 2).

Superior fracture type (Le Fort III). The most severe clinical picture is observed when the facial skeleton is completely broken in the subbasal type. In this case, in addition to profuse bleeding from the nose, mouth and ears, there is almost always a full-blown "flattening" and elongation of the face due to downshift of the upper jaw and zygomatic bones and consequently the bottom of the eye pits together with the eyeballs. The fracture line goes through the nasolabial suture, along the inner wall of the eye pit to the superior or inferior orbital fissure. Then along the outer wall of the eye pit to the frontozygomatic suture. Then goes to the back and down the greater wing of the sphenoid bone and reaches the upper part of the pterygoid process of sphenoid bone. The zygomatic processes of the temporal bones are fractured. In this type of fracture there is a separation of the facial bones from the skull of the brain (Fig. 3).

Figure 3. Guerin's fracture superior type according to Le Fort III

A.M. Bayramkulova (2005) analyzed the conclusions of medico-legal examinations of upper jaw fractures in living persons and followed Le Faure's classification. In the conclusion she noted, that taking into account the significant number of cases of craniofacial trauma, including upper jaw fractures, the complexity and severity of the damage caused to the health of the victims, we should pay much more attention to both the quality of medical records and the execution of the medico-legal reports. The importance of this is due to the legal needs that require accurate and objective presentation of expert information.

A.I. Avdeev and N.Y. Kompanets (2016), based on analysis of data on victims with craniofacial trauma, identified three groups of combined injuries: severe facial injuries are combined with mild TBI; facial skeletal injuries are combined with severe TBI; facial injuries of varying severity without signs of TBI.

Although there are many variations of the proposed classifications, in practice the classification of R. Le Fort (1901) is more commonly used, according to which upper jaw fractures are bilateral and their lines go symmetrically.

Thus, there are currently a variety of classifications of Guerin's fractures, which are mainly developed by clinicians. The existing medico-legal classifications do not fully reflect the injury variants and expert aspects. The variety of upper jaw injuries demands the adoption of a unified medico-legal classification that embodies all the necessary criteria.

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